

(Re-)Forging the Science of *Bayān*: ‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Ġurġānī in the Early Twentieth Century*

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Abstract

‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Ġurġānī took center stage in the field of *bayān* (called as well *balāġa*) during the first half of the twentieth century thanks, above all, to the efforts of Muḥammad ‘Abduh and Hellmut Ritter. As similar as they are in their approach, ‘Abduh and Ritter came to represent two mutually dismissive scholarly traditions with respect to Ġurġānī and the science of *bayān*. These two apparently divergent traditions, wittingly or unwittingly, contributed to forging one and the same image of Ġurġānī and *bayān*. As I attempt to show in this paper, this image that still prevails in the scholarly discourse was built under the shadow of *falsafa*.

Keywords: ‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Ġurġānī, *bayān*, *falsafa* (philosophy), Muḥammad ‘Abduh, Hellmut Ritter, historiography

Introduction

But into the subtleties of the mythologists it is not worth our while to inquire seriously; those, however, who use the language of proof we must cross-examine. [Aristotle, *Metaphysics*, 1000a, 18-20]

The science of *bayān* (*lit.* expressiveness), also called *balāġa*,¹ first gained momentum around the twelfth century, when numerous scholars across the Islamic world transformed it

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1 *Bayān* commonly refers both to this science as a whole, and also to one specific part of it, along with *ma‘ānī* (and *badī‘*), in the bipartite (or tripartite) conception of this science, especially after al-Sakkākī. In this study, I use this designation at the expense of the more popular *balāġa*. Even though both are supported by textual evidence, *balāġa* has been often associated with the Aristotelian *Rhetoric* (usually translated as *ḥaṭāba*), as its Arabic counterpart. For a brief account on the concept and history of this science see Thomas Bauer, “Rhetorik: arabische Kultur,” in *Rhetorik: Historisches Wörterbuch der Rhetorik*, ed. Gert Ueding (Tübingen: Max Niemeyer, 2007), 111-37. For an incisive study on the concept

by summarizing, further elaborating on, or criticizing the two works by ‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Ġurġānī (d. 1078), *Dalā’il al-i’ġāz* (*Proofs of the Inimitability*) and *Asrār al-balāġa* (*Mysteries of Eloquence*).² The numerous works written during this first flourishing of *bayān* subsequently overshadowed Ġurġānī’s own writings for centuries. Even though the intellectual engagement with Ġurġānī’s works was diverse and calls for further investigation, one particular line beginning with Abū Ya‘qūb al-Sakkākī’s (d. 1229) *Miftāḥ al-‘ulūm* enjoyed popularity and pre-eminence until the early twentieth century.³ Then, in the first half of this century (roughly speaking), two scholars from two different continents forcefully brought Ġurġānī back into the foreground within their respective contexts: Muḥammad ‘Abduh (1849-1905) from Egypt and Hellmut Ritter (1892-1971) from Germany. Due to their persistent efforts, Ġurġānī took center stage and remained central in a new era of *bayān* scholarship. Aside from acknowledging this undeniable achievement, I will connect these two figures, as far as necessary, with their immediate and more distant scholarly contexts, in Egypt and Europe respectively, to bring out more clearly their innovations and also borrowings, whether acknowledged or not.

As similar as these two influential figures are in their approach, ‘Abduh and Ritter came to represent two divergent and mutually dismissive scholarly traditions with respect to Ġurġānī and the science of *bayān*. ‘Abduh, for his part, exemplifies those scholars who identify themselves with Ġurġānī or even see themselves as his rightful heirs, aspiring to revive his heritage. One might dub them the “insiders.” By contrast, Ritter represents those non-native experts of Arabic (or orientalists) aiming to undertake a scholarly study of Ġurġānī’s works. These figures could be labeled the “outsiders.”⁴ The “outsiders” suspect the “insiders” of lacking critical vision.⁵ Then again, the “insiders” see the “outsiders” as

of *bayān* from a new perspective with a focus on Ibn Wahb, see Nadja Germann, “Was ist der Mensch? Zu Ishāq b. Ibrāhīm b. Wahbs Begriff von *bayān*,” forthcoming.

- 2 For the editions of these two works, see ‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Ġurġānī, *Asrār al-Balāġa: The Mysteries of Eloquence*, ed. Hellmut Ritter (Istanbul: Government Press, 1954) and ‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Ġurġānī, *Dalā’il al-i’ġāz*, ed. Maḥmūd Muḥammad Šākīr (Cairo: Maṭba‘at al-madani, 1984¹, 1992³).
- 3 For a list of traditional authors in this line up to the twentieth century, see Aḥmad Muṣṭafā al-Marāġī, *Tārīḥ ‘ulūm al-balāġa wa-l-ta’rīf bi-riġālihā* (Cairo: Muṣṭafā al-Bābī al-Ḥalabī, 1950), esp. 58ff. For a standard history of the development of this science in the Islamic world, see Šawqī Dayf, *al-Balāġa: taṭawwur wa-tārīḥ* (Cairo: Dār al-ma‘ārif, 1965), esp. 160-270 (= ch. 3) and 271-367 (= ch. 4). In a special issue of the *Journal of Abbasid Studies*, a group of scholars problematized this monolithic history of Ġurġānī’s reception, see Joseph E. Lowry, Monique Bernards and Alexander Key (eds.), *Journal of Abbasid Studies*, 5.1-2 (2018), special issue on ‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Jurġānī; see there in particular Avigail Noy, “The Legacy of ‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Jurġānī in the Arabic East before al-Qazwīnī’s Talkhīṣ al-Miftāḥ,” *Journal of Abbasid Studies*, 5.1-2 (2018), 11-57.
- 4 For a collective scholarly effort to go beyond such ungrounded and mutually exclusive categorizations that have marred the apologetic, polemic and even the supposedly non-partisan academic approach in the study of the various strands of thought in the Islamic world, see Majid Daneshgar and Aaron W. Hughes (eds.), *Deconstructing Islamic Studies* (Boston: Ilex Foundation, 2020).
- 5 The French orientalist Régis Blachère, for instance, refers to the “édition égyptienne” of Ġurġānī’s *Asrār* as “très médiocre.” See Régis Blachère, “Review of *Asrār al-balāġa*, by ‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Ġurġānī, ed. Hellmut Ritter,” *Arabica*, 4.3 (1957), 314. Hellmut Ritter, the German editor and translator of the *Asrār*, however, remains neutral on the “Egyptian” edition and makes use of it for his own edition. See Hellmut Ritter, “Introduction,” in *Asrār al-Balāġa. The Mysteries of Eloquence*, ed. Hellmut Ritter (Istanbul:

alien to Ğurġānī's indigenous cultural space and accordingly portray them, even in their greatest scholarly endeavors, as merely groping their way up the dark and slippery paths of the Arabic language.⁶ I will show in this study how these two apparently divergent groups of "insiders" and "outsiders", wittingly or unwittingly, contributed to forging one and the same image of Ğurġānī, an image which still prevails in the scholarly discourse about him. Through the example of Ğurġānī, moreover, I aim to demonstrate the inseparability of the history and historiography of *falsafa* (an Arabicized loan word from the Classical Greek *philosophia* designating the Greek-inspired philosophical tradition in the Islamic world) and *bayān*.

1. *Bayān* in the Islamic World

1.1. Reviving the "Queen of Sciences" to Revive the Islamic World

People of our lands [western Islamic lands, particularly the author's homeland Egypt...] could dispense with that [i.e. the acquisition of *bayān*] thanks to the innate sound taste (*al-dawq al-salīm*) bestowed to them by God [...]. Peoples of the eastern lands, however, who have the upper hand in sciences, particularly rational sciences and logic, exhausted their high-aspiring endeavor in the acquisition of this science [i.e. *bayān*]. [*Subkī*, attempting to justify the rarity of eminent scholars of *balāġa* in western Muslim lands].⁷

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At the turn of the twentieth century, Muḥammad 'Abduh renounced the eight-century-old tradition of *bayān*-scholarship that predominated in his time in the Islamic world and set out to claim pride of place in this domain for Ğurġānī's two works instead. To achieve this aim, he had to eliminate the widely disseminated products of this longlived scholarship from circulation: Its roots reached back to *Miftāḥ al-ʿulūm*, the celebrated work of Abū Ya'qūb al-Sakkākī (d. 1229), and its most recent offshoot, within a still-thriving commentary tradition, was the work of 'Abduh's contemporary and fellow Azharī scholar Šams al-Dīn Muḥammad al-Inbānī (d. 1896) on the commentary by Sa'd al-Dīn al-Taftāzānī (d. 1390) on al-Ḥaṭīb al-Qazwīnī's (d. 1338) abridgement of Sakkākī's above-mentioned work. The super-commentator Inbānī happened to also be the Grand Imam, the rector so to speak, of al-Azhar, one of the most influential educational centers in the Islamic world.⁸ No change in the curriculum of al-Azhar was possible without his permission, as its highest authority. At the time, the official textbook for the study of *balāġa*, which was allocated during three academic years from the eighth to the tenth grade in the thirteen-year study plan of al-Azhar, was

Government Press, 1954), 25; Hellmut Ritter, "Einführung," in *Die Geheimnisse der Wortkunst (Asrār al-balāġa)*, transl. by Hellmut Ritter (Wiesbaden: Franz Steiner, 1959), 17.

6 This is how the third Egyptian editor of Ğurġānī's works, Abū Fahad Maḥmūd Šākīr describes Hellmut Ritter; see Maḥmūd Muḥammad Šākīr, "Muqaddima," in *Asrār al-Balāġa*, ed. Maḥmūd Muḥammad Šākīr (Cairo: Maṭba'at al-madanī, 1991), 8-9.

7 Bahā' al-Dīn al-Subkī, *Arūs al-afrāḥ fī šarḥ Talḥīṣ al-Miftāḥ*, ed. 'Abd al-Ḥamīd Hindāwī (Beirut: al-Dār al-namūdaġiyya, 2003), 1: 20-1.

8 Inbānī was the Grand Imam of al-Azhar for two terms, 1881-1882 and 1886-1895.

Taftāzānī's commentary along with that of Inbānī.⁹ 'Abduh had attempted to convince him to introduce new textbooks into its curriculum, albeit with no success; to the Grand Imam, the firmly established "practice" was not open to negotiation.¹⁰ 'Abduh began teaching Ğurġānī's *Dalā'il* and *Asrār* at al-Azhar only after the death of Inbānī, thus marking the beginning of an incremental academic interest in the theoretical output of Ğurġānī in the century to come.

'Abduh's canonization of Ğurġānī's works over the last decade of his life through the creation of a critical edition, their oral analysis and explication in lecture courses, and their broad dissemination at the expense of the established textbooks written by later commentators, was at the core of his lifelong struggle to reform the Arabic language. In his autobiography, 'Abduh counts linguistic reform and religious reform as the two great reforms that he called for and endeavored to achieve throughout his life.¹¹ However, these two aspects of his program for reform, together with a third political aspect that he mentions on the side, are deeply interwoven. 'Abduh firmly believed that the attainment of Islam's urgently needed sound religious reform, crucial for its political existence, hinged solely on linguistic reform and the revival of the Arabic language.¹² He thus intertwined the linguistic, religious, and political elements in his reform program to an extent that distinguishes him from other religious reformers both inside and outside the Islamic world.¹³

If we contrast him with Martin Luther, for instance, to whom he has been often compared, one main difference stands out.¹⁴ While Luther brought his people's holy scripture down from the heavens of Latin by translating it into vernacular German, thus freeing it from the hands of priests and putting it within reach of the faithful, 'Abduh set out to elevate the language of his people towards the unreachable heavens of Quranic language; Ğurġānī

9 See, for instance, the table of subject matters at al-Azhar from May 1900 in Muḥammad 'Alī Ḥilla, *al-Azhar fī l-arṣīf al-Miṣrī: waṭā'iḳ min al-qarnayn al-tāsi-'aṣar wa-l-iṣrīn* (Cairo: Dār al-kutub wa-l-waṭā'iḳ al-qawmiyya, 2015), 406-12, here 410.

10 Ever since his early days at al-Azhar, especially after his association with Ğamāl al-Dīn al-Afġānī, 'Abduh has been seeking to reform this institution. For his attempts to convince Inbānī, see Mohammad 'Abduh, *al-A'māl al-kāmila*, ed. Muḥammad 'Imāra (Beirut: Dār al-ṣurūq, 1993), 3: 193.

11 'Abduh, *al-A'māl*, 2: 310. Only recently, 'Abduh's emphasis on language reform has begun to attract some scholarly attention, see now Ahmed El Shamsy, *Rediscovering the Islamic Classics: How Editors and Print Culture Transformed an Intellectual Tradition* (Princeton, Oxford: Princeton University Press, 2020), esp. 147-58.

12 *Al-A'māl*, 1: 867: "inna mā yaḥtāġuhu l-kiyān al-siyāsī al-islāmī laysa muġarrad al-iṣlāḥāt wa-innamā l-iṣlāḥ al-dīnī al-ṣaḥīḥ."

13 In his study on the concept of 'society' within the context of Islamic reformism, Florian Zemmin delves into various aspects related to 'Abduh's role in shaping this discourse, with a particular focus on the influential journal *al-Manār*, see Florian Zemmin, *Modernity in Islamic Tradition: The concept of 'society' in the journal al-Manār* (Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter, 2018).

14 For representing 'Abduh as the Martin Luther of the Islamic world, see, for instance, 'Abdallāh al-'Arwī, *al-Idiyūlūġiyyā al-'arabiyya al-mu'āṣira* (Beirut: al-Markaz al-ṭaqāfī al-'arabī, 1995), 61. From another perspective, Assem Hefny emphasizes the closeness of 'Abduh's concept and agenda of reformation (*iṣlāḥ*) in the Islamic world with Martin Luther from various perspectives; see Assem Hefny, "Die islamische Rezeption der Reformation," in *Reformation im Islam: Perspektiven und Grenzen*, ed. Jürgen Erik Klusmann et al. (Wiesbaden: Springer VS, 2019), 45-58. 'Abduh himself was critical of Luther and a Protestant approach to religious reform, see, for instance, *al-A'māl*, 3: 292-3.

provided him with the ladder he needed to take them to that height.¹⁵ But then again, in contrast to his own mentor Ġamāl al-Dīn al-Afġānī (d. 1897), who never shied away from directly confronting the sources of the Muslim world’s political plight, ‘Abduh focused his energy on remedying what he saw as the cause of this suffering from the inside, as well as on religious authorities and institutions that he blamed for the continuation of this suffering. Accordingly, his anti-imperialist and Pan-Islamist program fundamentally differed from that of Afġānī. For ‘Abduh, the cause of suffering was nothing other than the prevailing tendency towards blind following (*taqlīd*) and intellectual stagnation (*ġumūd*), both of which he viewed as symptoms of a severe, historically rooted malady, namely the de-Arabicization of Islam under the lasting dominion of non-Arabs, including, among others, Turkic and Iranian peoples (*al-turk wa-l-daylam*).¹⁶ While reducing ‘Abduh’s whole reform agenda to linguistic reform might be a stretch, for him, language was literally a matter of life and death, as he once emphasized: “A nation with a dead language has no life.”¹⁷

In this spirit, ‘Abduh saw Ġurġānī’s works as a fountain of life that could revitalize the Arabic language and through this Islam, as an originally Arabic religion. To put it in ‘Abduh’s own terms, to be an Arabic religion was the highest distinction of Islam. It was only due to this distinction that Muslims gained the highest glory—during the so-called Islamic Golden Age—and were able to assimilate Greek science within the space of a mere century, naturalizing it as Arabic science. Unlike their European counterparts, who required ten centuries, “Arabs could not accept to be mere students of Aristotle, Plato, Euclid, and Ptolemy for a long time.”¹⁸ The decadence of Islamic civilization began when Muslims lost this Arabic element. ‘Abduh even pinned down the precise beginning of this decline: the decision of the Abbasid caliph al-Mu’taṣim (d. 842) to mobilize non-Arab peoples in his army and to include them in his government at the expense of the Arabs, who were presumably sympathetic to the ‘Alawites who opposed him, on account of their closer kinship with the prophet of Islam. This was the beginning of the process of “de-Arabicization of Islam and thus making it unintelligible” (*hunāka stuġīma l-islām wa-nqalaba ‘aġamiyyan*). The power this caliph thus conferred on foreigners gradually expanded, growing until the sack of Baghdad in 1258. The harmful consequences of this policy, however, extended far beyond this date. It implanted in people’s minds—to cite one major harmful consequence—the idea that “the antecedent shall not hold anything but what the precedent held.”¹⁹ This idea turned

15 By reviving the original language of the Muslims, ‘Abduh aspired as well to grant Muslims an unmediated access to their holy scripture, the Quran, the return to which was central in his reform. The consequent centrality of the Quran in the scholarly activities of both ‘Abduh and Riḍā is often overlooked. Johanna Pink incisively highlights this aspect in both scholars at various stages of the scholarship; see Johanna Pink, “‘Abduh, Muḥammad,” in *Encyclopaedia of the Qur’ān*, ed. Jane Dammen McAuliffe (Washington DC: Georgetown University, 2015), consulted online on February 17, 2022, via http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1875-3922_q3_EQCOM_050483; Johanna Pink, “Riḍā, Raṣīd,” *ibid.*, consulted online on February 17, 2022, http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1875-3922_q3_EQCOM_050503.

16 ‘Abduh, *al-A’māl*, 3: 335-6.

17 ‘Abduh, *al-A’māl*, 4: 16: “lā ḥayat^{um} li-umma^{um} mātat luġatuhā.”

18 ‘Abduh, *al-A’māl*, 3: 323.

19 ‘Abduh, *al-A’māl*, 3: 336: “qarrarū anna l-muta’ahḥir laysa lahu an yaqūl^u bi-ġayrⁱ mā yaqūl^u l-mutaqaddim.”

into a doctrinal belief in the Islamic world and caused the total cessation of thought and the stagnation of minds, or as he puts it elsewhere, blind following (*taqlīd*) and intellectual stagnation (*ġumūd*).²⁰ All branches of Islamic knowledge were thus corrupted.

In the same manner, *bayān* too underwent a process of decline. In the view of ‘Abduh, the works that he strove to remove from circulation were the product of such a stagnant historical period and of a mindset conditioned and contaminated by this fundamental dogmatic idea lying behind the prevalent phenomenon of de-Arabization or foreignness (*istiġām*, *uġma*). ‘Abduh’s persistent struggle for educational reform under the influence of his mentor Afġānī caused—in part due to his relation to Afġānī—fierce conflict between him and his conservative Azharī peers. They were quick to depict his denunciation of these authorities as unprecedented innovation (*bid’a*). ‘Abduh, however, saw things the other way round:

They say seeking to change paths is looking after the recently developed (*al-ġadīd*) and craving inventions [with no past precedent] (*bid’a*) [...]. This is not true. The recently developed, the [unprecedented] invention is what we see them following, with its obvious repercussions and prevailing harm.

After throwing their charge back at them, he states:

What we call for is what was truly established in ancient times (*al-qadīm al-ḥaqīqī*). Without our reliance on that, we shall have no success.²¹

Since such sources and authors had been lost or were inaccessible, ‘Abduh sought to rehabilitate them by reviving the heritage of the “intermittent centuries” (*al-qurūn al-mutawassiṭa*) of Islamic history. This fluid “intermittent” period included a set of scholars and works from different eras which, in ‘Abduh’s eyes, offered a unique vantage point from which to look at the lost heritage of the earliest Islamic centuries, which were not yet contaminated by later developments suffering from *uġma* and *taqlīd*. “By going back to the sources from the intermittent [Islamic] centuries,” he states on one occasion,

we are accomplishing a step towards reforming the books [...]. As long as we are constrained to the expressions of the currently circulating books, as the only sources of our religion and knowledge, we will gain nothing but more ignorance.²²

Al-Muḥaṣṣaṣ, the linguistic encyclopedia of Ibn Sīdah al-Mursī (d. 1066), *Maqāmāt*, the literary work attributed to Badī’ al-Zamān al-Hamaḍānī (d. 1007), and *al-Baṣā’ir al-Naṣīriyya fī l-manṭiq*, the logical work by Ibn Sahlān al-Sāwī (early twelfth century) all belonged to this

²⁰ ‘Abduh, *al-A’māl*, 3: 335-6.

²¹ ‘Abduh, *al-A’māl*, 3: 161: “yaqūlu l-qā’ilūn inna ṭalab taġyīr al-turuq i’tinā²⁰ⁿ bi-l-ġadīd wa-wulū²¹ⁿ bi-l-bida’ aw nuzū²²ⁿ lahā. Wa-laysa l-amr kaḍālik, fa-inna l-ġadīd wa-l-bid’a huwa mā narāhum ‘alayhi wa-qad ṣahara aṭaruhu wa-‘amma ḍararuh. Fa-l-qadīm al-ḥaqīqī huwa mā nad’ū ilayh wa-lā naġāh²³ lanā illā bi-l-ta’wīl ‘alayh.”

²² ‘Abduh, *al-A’māl*, 3: 214: “idā raġa’nā ilā kutub al-qurūn al-wuṣṭā [...] nakūnu qad ḥatawnā ḥuṭwa²⁴ⁿ li-īṣlāh al-kutub wa-l-fiqh, wa-mā dumnā muqayyadīn bi-‘ibārāt ḥāḍiḥi l-kutub al-mutadāwila wa-lā na’rif al-dīn wa-l-‘ilm illā minhā fa-lā nazdādu illā ġahlan.”

collection. However, his editorial output also included earlier classical works, such as the juridical Mālikī work *al-Mudawwana* or the *Nahğ al-balāğa* of ‘Alī b. Abī Ṭālib.

In the field of *balāğa*, the works of Ğurğānī represented for ‘Abduh this pristine state of Islamic knowledge. Just like the numerous other central texts mentioned above, the edition and publication of Ğurğānī’s two works were accomplished within the framework of the activities of The Society of the Revival of Arabic Science (*Ġam‘iyyat ihyā’ al-‘ulūm al-‘arabiyya*) that ‘Abduh founded in 1900, one year after becoming the grand *muftī*, or the highest legal authority, of Egypt in 1899.²³ He was the main theorist and scientific authority behind the project to edit, publish, and disseminate Ğurğānī’s two works, even though he enjoyed the selfless support of his disciples. Rašīd Riḍā (1865–1935), to name but one, was the main executive director behind this collective achievement.²⁴ When the latter moved to Egypt in 1898 to found the periodical *al-Manār* (The Lighthouse),²⁵ ‘Abduh was already engaged in the edition of Ğurğānī’s *Dalā’il*. He had fetched two manuscripts from Medina and Baghdad to compare them with the one available to him in Cairo to prepare his edition of this work, as Riḍā reports.²⁶ It appears, however, that his first choice had been Ğurğānī’s other work, the *Asrār*. He had settled on *Dalā’il* due to his failure to find any manuscripts of the former work. Hence, as soon as Rašīd Riḍā informed him of the existence of a manuscript of that work in Tripolis, a copy owned by a friend of his, the literary scholar ‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Mağribī, ‘Abduh urged him to procure it and prepare it for publication. Riḍā set to work, found a second manuscript from Istanbul, and prepared the edition of *Asrār* in a couple of years. In 1901, he published the work with Taraqqī Press in Cairo and distributed it in April 1902. ‘Abduh’s lectures at al-Azhar, first on this work and then on *Dalā’il*, before, during, and after the whole process, functioned as a parallel laboratory for their edition and reworking of the two works. In addition to a host of advanced students, other scholars and lecturers at al-Azhar, as well as teachers of public schools enthusiastically attended these lectures. One year later, in 1903, *Dalā’il* was published with ‘Abduh and Muḥammad Maḥmūd al-Tarkazī al-Šinqīī as joint editors, in collaboration with Rašīd Riḍā.

The rationale behind this whole project that was accomplished in a relatively short time was the following: In contrast to those conservative ‘*ulamā*’ who fought to preserve the long commentary tradition on Ğurğānī’s works, ‘Abduh, and others under his influence, completely dismissed this commentary tradition as corrupted by non-natives and Greek-inspired scholars, calling for the restoration of long-lost Arabic taste. They depicted these works that had been developed based on the writings of Ğurğānī as an unnatural hyper-theoretical and overly philosophical interpretation of *bayān* by “a crowd of people settled and rooted in *falsafa*.” While seeing their dominance in the educational curricula as a sign of “corruption of taste in language,” they devalued these textbooks as marred by ‘*uğma* and

23 ‘Abduh, *al-‘Amāl*, 1: 34, 198, for instance.

24 Consider ‘Abduh’s letter to Rašīd Riḍā, from August 28, 1901, instructing him to write the introduction to their edition of *Asrār* with some additional remarks concerning the process, in: ‘Abduh, *al-‘Amāl*, 1: 878.

25 For a study on the historical establishment of *al-Manār* in the context of religious reform, see Umar Ryad, “A Printed Muslim ‘Lighthouse’ in Cairo: al-Manār’s Early Years, Religious Aspiration and Reception (1898-1903),” *Arabica*, 56 (2009), 27-60.

26 Aside from these basic descriptions, no further information is given concerning the manuscripts that were used for the edition.

went so far as to represent them as “dead inscriptions that ignorance had named science.” Hence, they called for abandoning these imitations and returning to the original lively sources of the Arabic language, thus rehabilitating the natural Arabic taste. They struggled, however, to revive the works of those earlier scholars whom they saw as the only source that could convey “uncorrupted taste” (*al-dawq al-salīm*).²⁷

We got confused from looking into technical meanings and exploring them excessively, to the extent that what lay behind them turned into a misfortune for our sciences and minds,

‘Abduh diagnoses, emphasizing that,

in a nutshell, the aim behind such Arabic sciences [meaning the linguistic sciences of *nahw* and *‘ilm al-ma‘ānī wa-l-bayān*] is to reach the same degree that Arabs possessed by natural disposition (*salīqa*).²⁸

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From this perspective, ‘Abduh sets out to reconstruct Ğurġānī’s project, in order to undo the harm and restore the natural disposition and linguistic taste of the Arabs, thus enabling them to re-Arabicize Islam.

This emphasis on taste and gustation (*dawq*, *taḍawwuq*), fundamentally linked to the natural disposition of the Arabs, entails the centrality of the Arabic language in *bayān*. Ironically, due to this emphasis, ‘Abduh comes close to Sakkākī, from whom he wanted to radically distance himself. Sakkākī, too, thought that the cognitive source for understanding the miraculous inimitability of the Quran, the presumed aim behind the science of *bayān*, “is nothing but taste” (*al-dawq laysa illā*).²⁹ ‘Abduh also echoes Sakkākī when he laments what the *muwalladūn*, those who are not pure Arabs, had done to the Arabic language.³⁰ In doing so, he considers himself to be expressing the lament of men of taste (*ahl al-dawq*) and their concern for the queen of all sciences: *balāġa*.³¹ Furthermore, when ‘Abduh set out to edit the Ğurġānīan texts equipped with his “Arab disposition and literary taste (*tab‘ ‘arabī wa-dawq adabī*),”³² he adopted a theoretical framework and structure for them that is Sakkākian in its core. ‘Abduh introduces these works as the foundational works of the science of *balāġa*,

27 For ‘Abduh’s relevant observations, see, for instance, his eulogy (*taqrīz*) of his student ‘Abd al-Raḥmān al-Barqūqī, published in the latter’s edition of al-Ḥaṭīb al-Qazwīnī’s *al-Talḥīs*; see Ġalāl al-Dīn Muḥammad b. ‘Abd al-Raḥmān al-Qazwīnī al-Ḥaṭīb, *al-Talḥīs*, ed. ‘Abd al-Raḥmān al-Barqūqī (Cairo: Maṭba‘at al-Nīl, 1904), 23-4. Also see Barqūqī’s introduction to the same edition (al-Qazwīnī, *al-Talḥīs*, 2-22) as well as Rašīd Riḍā’s prologue and epilogue to the editions of *Asrār* and *Dalā’il*, respectively; see Muḥammad Rašīd Riḍā, “Muqaddima,” in *Asrār al-balāġa: fī ‘ilm al-bayān*, ed. Muḥammad Rašīd Riḍā (Cairo: Maṭba‘at al-taraqqī, 1902), *bā’-ḥā’*; Muḥammad Rašīd Riḍā, “Ḥātima,” in *Dalā’il al-i‘ğāz: fī ‘ilm al-ma‘ānī*, ed. Muḥammad ‘Abduh, Muḥammad Maḥmūd al-Tarkazī al-Šinqīṭī, in collaboration with Muḥammad Rašīd Riḍā (Cairo: Maṭba‘at al-mawsū‘āt, 1913), 402-4.

28 ‘Abduh, *al-A‘māl*, 3: 156.

29 Abū Ya‘qūb al-Sakkākī, *Miftāḥ al-‘ulūm*, ed. Na‘īm Zarzūr (Beirut: Dār al-kutub al-‘ilmiyya, 1983¹, 1987²), 416.

30 Al-Sakkākī, *Miftāḥ*, 416.

31 ‘Abduh, *al-A‘māl*, 1: 190-1.

32 ‘Abduh, *al-A‘māl*, 1: 198.

which, according to his bipartite conceptual framework, consists of *bayān* and *ma'ānī* as its two main branches. Accordingly, he designates *Asrār* and *Dalā'il* with the subtitles “concerning the science of *ma'ānī*” and “concerning the science of *bayān*,” respectively. This bifurcation can be traced back at least to al-Zamaḥṣārī (d. 1144), whom ‘Abduh praised for his “precise linguistic analysis,”³³ just as the tripartite conceptualization of *balāga* (*ma'ānī*, *bayān*, *badī'*) is a residuum of the Sakkākian reading of Ğurġānī in ‘Abduh.³⁴

Moreover, by submitting to this Sakkākian influence, ‘Abduh turns out to also perpetuate the “ancient quarrel between philosophy and poetry.” This fundamental and unbridgeable divide between the language of proof and the language of taste, prevalent in the tradition of *falsafa*, derives from the distinction between intellect and imagination and their corresponding separate epistemic spheres. This distinction dates back as far as Plato’s differentiation of the philosopher and the rhetorician/sophist in his *Gorgias* and *Phaedrus*.³⁵ In the Greek context, this conceptual pair distinguished philosophy from literature, and it lived on within the *falsafa* tradition in the Islamic world. Major thinkers in this tradition, from Kindī (d. 873) through Fārābī (d. 950) to Ibn Sīnā (d. 1037), elaborated a theoretical account building on the distinction between the corresponding two faculties of the soul to distinguish philosophy not only from literature, but more specifically from religion, which was conceptualized as existing within a contrasting literary domain.³⁶ Thinkers in this

33 El Shamsy, *Rediscovering the Islamic Classics*, 152. Maḥmūd al-Zamaḥṣārī (d. 1143) indicates this bipartite conception of the science of *balāga*, as consisting of *ilm al-ma'ānī* and *ilm al-bayān*, both in his well-known exegetical work *al-Kaššāf* as well as his *Asās al-balāga*. See Maḥmūd al-Zamaḥṣārī, *Asās al-balāga*, ed. Muḥammad Bāsil ‘Uyūn al-Sūd (Beirut: Dār al-kutub al-‘ilmiyya, 1998), 1: 16; Maḥmūd al-Zamaḥṣārī, *al-Kaššāf ‘an ḥaqā’iq al-tanzīl wa-‘uyūn al-aqāwīl fī wuġūh al-ta’wīl*, ed. Ḥalīl Ma’mūn Šīḥā (Beirut: Dār al-ma’rifa, 2009³), 23. In neither occasion is there any mention of Ğurġānī. He does cite him once by name, but only in reference to his poetry; cf. Zamaḥṣārī, *al-Kaššāf*, 1048.

34 In the third part of his *Mafātīh al-‘ulūm*, al-Sakkākī divides the science of *balāga* into the sciences of meanings (*ilm al-ma'ānī*), and expressiveness (*ilm al-bayān*) and a third section under the title “manners employed to enhance the speech” (*wuġūh yu’tā bihā li-taḥsīn al-kalām*) that is later dubbed “*al-badī'*,” probably for the first time in *al-Miṣbāḥ* of Badr al-Dīn b. Mālik (d. 1287); see Badr al-Dīn b. Mālik, *al-Miṣbāḥ fī l-ma'ānī wa-l-bayān wa-l-badī'*, ed. ‘Abd al-Ḥamīd Hindāwī (Beirut: Dār al-kutub al-‘ilmiyya, 2001), esp. 99.

35 The thematic connection between *Gorgias* and *Phaedrus* and their focus on the nature and limitations of rhetoric is commonly acknowledged. For a systematic study on this thematic interconnectedness, see Tushar Irani, *Plato on the Value of Philosophy: The Art of Argument in the Gorgias and Phaedrus* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2017); cf. Seth Benardete, *The Rhetoric of Morality and Philosophy: Plato’s Gorgias and Phaedrus* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2009); Marina McCoy, *Plato on the Rhetoric of Philosophers and Sophists* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2008). Concerning the oscillation of scholars as to the profession of Gorgias between rhetorician and sophist, see Jacqueline Tusi, “Between Rhetoric and Sophistry: The Puzzling Case of Plato’s Gorgias,” *Apeiron*, 53.1 (2020), 59-80. For a general analysis of Plato’s discussions on rhetoric and poetry in *Republic* and *Ion* besides the two mentioned great dialogues on rhetoric, see Charles L. Griswold, “Plato on Rhetoric and Poetry,” in *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (spring 2020 edition), ed. Edward N. Zalta, consulted online on February 17, 2022, via <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2020/entries/plato-rhetoric/>.

36 For the psychological account of prophecy in the philosophical works of these thinkers see Richard Walzer, “Al-Fārābī’s Theory of Prophecy and Divination,” *The Journal of Hellenic Studies*, 77.1 (1957), 142-8; M. E. Marmura, “Avicenna’s Theory of Prophecy in the Light of Aš‘arite Theology,” in *The Seed of Wisdom: Essays in Honour of T. J. Meek*, ed. William Stewart McCullough (Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1964), 165-74; James Winston Morris, “The Philosopher-Prophet in Avicenna’s Political

Hellenic paradigm saw the works of the Greek philosopher Aristotle as the product of intellect, contrasting them with the book of the Arab prophet Muḥammad, which they saw as an artifact produced by a poet, representing the fruit of his imagination. Thus, they managed to combine the profile of the philosopher with that of the prophet/poet. At the same time, however, they persistently kept the demonstrative and poetic discourses apart. Within this theoretical framework, the Quran—which itself repudiates its identification with “the diction of a poet”—was lumped together with the poetical heritage of the ancient Arabs. While the former used the language of proof, the latter was the language of taste. This divide, at work even in the edition of Ğurġānī’s works, becomes sharper after ‘Abduh.

1.2. Liberating Arabic to Modernize the Arab World

‘Abduh was forced to interrupt his lectures at al-Azhar in the face of threats from Egypt’s Khedive (ruling prince) directed at any reformist initiative or movement, hoping for a better day to come, a day he might have seen had he not lost his life to cancer that same year (1905). Nonetheless, he continued to inspire later generations of scholars after his death, both inside and outside Islamist circles. What proved most inspiring was his confrontation with al-Azhar, in which he aimed to revive the Islamic world by questioning orthodox authorities and uncritically established authoritative works in various fields, as well as his perseverance in replacing them with ones that he saw worthy of such a status. Other religious scholars, such as Muḥammad Rašīd Riḍā and ‘Abd al-Raḥmān al-Barbūqī, continued down the path he laid specifically in this domain by preparing re-editions or new editions of central works in the tradition of *bayān*. Under his shadow, these scholars remained captive to the ethnic bias underpinning the presumed centrality of the Arabic *taste* in Ğurġānī’s project.

However, ‘Abduh’s influence was much broader. Later on, numerous scholars and intellectuals took his critique of established authorities further.³⁷ Ṭāhā Ḥusayn, the first graduate of the Egyptian University in 1914³⁸—who was expelled from al-Azhar in 1908 after six turbulent years when he had just begun taking *balāġa* courses³⁹—represents a radical reverberation of ‘Abduh’s critical approach. He took up where ‘Abduh had left off. Not only did he undermine the originality, i.e., the pure Arabic origin, of Ğurġānī himself let alone his commentators, but he also systematically criticized the authenticity of the *ġāhili* poetry,⁴⁰

Philosophy,” in *Political Aspects of Islamic Philosophy: Essays in Honor of Muhsin S. Mahdi*, ed. Charles E. Butterworth (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1992), 152-98 (= ch. 4), esp. 187ff. For the later development of Avicenna’s psychological and socio-political theory of prophecy in the theological context with a focus on Faḥr al-Dīn al-Rāzī (d. 1210), see Ayman Shihadeh, “Aspects of the Reception of Avicenna’s Theory of Prophecy in Islamic Theology,” *Proceedings of the American Catholic Philosophical Association*, 86 (2012), 23-32.

37 Consider Ḥusayn’s critique at the end of his *Fī l-šīr al-ġāhili* of the prevalent idea that “the ancient is better than the new.” Ṭāhā Ḥusayn, *Fī l-šīr al-ġāhili* (Cairo: Dār al-kutub al-Miṣriyya, 1926), 129-30; cf. ‘Abduh, *al-A’māl*, 3: 336.

38 Ṭāhā Ḥusayn, *Mudakkirāt Ṭāhā Ḥusayn* (Beirut: Dār al-ādāb, 1967), 96.

39 For Ḥusayn’s own eloquent and entertaining account of these years, see Ḥusayn, *Mudakkirāt*, 5-25.

40 On *ġāhili* poetry (and prose), see Ġāzī Ṭulaymāt and ‘Irfān al-Ašqar, *al-Adab al-ġāhili: qaḍāyāhu, aġrāḍuhu, a’lāmuhu, funūnuhu* (Hims: Dār al-iršād, 1992); Kamal Abu-Deeb, “Towards a Structural Analysis of Pre-Islamic Poetry,” *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, 6 (1975), 148-84; id., “Towards a Structural Analysis of Pre-Islamic Poetry (II): the Eros Vision,” *Edebiyât*, 1 (1976), 3-69.

calling into question the very notion of “Arabness.” Concerning the poetry of the pre-Islamic era, which was considered the pure achievement of the Arabs before the arrival of the Greek sciences in the Islamic world and thus the most authoritative source for the Arabic language, he declared that

[t]he absolute majority of what we call *ġāhilī* poetry, has no share of *Ġāhiliyya*. It was rather fabricated and manipulated after the advent of Islam. Thus, it is rather Islamic and represents the life of Muslims and their tendencies and desires more than it represents life during *Ġāhiliyya*.⁴¹

In doing so, he created room for a constant presence of the Greeks, in one form or another, in the history of Arabic *adab*⁴² and *bayān* ever since its presumed beginnings.

In his view, down to the age of Abū ‘Utmān al-Ġāhiz (d. 868) in roughly the mid-ninth century, *bayān* consisted of three different elements: Arabic, Persian, and Greek.⁴³ The Hellenic influence on *bayān* occurred indirectly through the Mu‘tazilite theologians, who, according to Ḥusayn, were the true founders of Arabic *bayān* thanks to their vast knowledge of Greek philosophy.⁴⁴ As to Arabic *adab*, this Greek influence reached a pinnacle at the hands of the poets and scribes of non-Arab origin, for instance Ibn al-Muqaffa‘ (d. 759) and Abū Tammām (d. 845), among others. These figures either directly used Greek sources or gained knowledge of them through their translations.⁴⁵ This set in motion a smooth process of Hellenization which would have evolved seamlessly “had those Arabs who were in charge of disseminating Greek philosophy remained within their bounds and kept a cautious eye, rather than transgressing the scope of theoretical speculation and stepping into *adab* itself to extend their dominance over it.” This happened particularly through the translation into Arabic of Aristotle’s two pertinent works, the *Rhetoric* and the *Poetics*.⁴⁶ According to Ḥusayn, the translation of these two works provoked the attacks of the poets and scribes on Aristotle’s logic.

After this first stage of *bayān*, which Ḥusayn describes as the unitary stage, the tradition developed into two contrasting lineages: a conservative Arabic *bayān* that seldom approached Greek philosophy and a separate Greek *bayān* that openly fell back on Aristotle. However, the first trend could not fully resist Greek influences. Ḥusayn mentions the well-known works *al-Badī‘* by Ibn al-Mu‘tazz (d. 908) and *Naqd al-šī‘r* by his contemporary Qudāma b. Ġa‘far (d. between ca. 932 and 948) as examples clearly exhibiting such an influence.⁴⁷ Thus, in his view, *bayān* developed into two contrasting Arabic and Greek camps

41 Ḥusayn, *Fī l-šī‘r al-ġāhilī*, 7, 9-10, 126, 180-3.

42 For a comprehensive history of *adab* in the pre-modern Islamic world, see Šawqī Dayf, *Tārīḥ al-adab al-‘arabī*, 10 vols. (Cairo: Dār al-ma‘ārif, 1960-1995).

43 Ṭāhā Ḥusayn, “Tamhīd fī l-bayān al-‘arabī min al-Ġāhiz ilā ‘Abd al-Qāhir,” transl. by ‘Abd al-Ḥamīd al-‘Ibādī, in *Naqd al-naṭr*, aw: *Kitāb al-bayān*, ed. ‘Abd al-Ḥamīd al-‘Ibādī (Beirut: Dār al-kutub al-‘ilmiyya, 1980), 7.

44 Ḥusayn, “Tamhīd fī l-bayān al-‘arabī,” 8.

45 Ḥusayn, *ibid.*, 9.

46 Ḥusayn, *ibid.*, 10.

47 Ḥusayn, “Tamhīd fī l-bayān al-‘arabī,” 11-2.

after having been an amalgam of Persian, Arabic, and Greek elements prior to the mid-ninth century. He claims that after this bipartition, an intensive Arabicization drive was set in motion to de-Hellenize *bayān* and make it utterly Arabic both in spirit and in content, as well as in the examples used. The aim of this process was to give the impression that “Arabic” *bayān* did not depend on any other one, and above all not on Greek *bayān*.

In this vein, Ṭāhā Ḥusayn disagreed with ‘Abduh (even though he was inspired by him), with Ḡāhiz, and with anyone who took *bayān* to be a “purely Arabic science.” While ‘Abduh denounces Ḡurḡānī’s commentators due to their rootedness in *falsafa*, in order to revive the works of the latter as the true representative of the *Arabic bayān*, Ḥusayn sees Ḡurḡānī himself as the main source for such a turn towards *falsafa* in the history of *bayān*. According to Ḥusayn, with Ḡurḡānī, *bayān* came closer to *falsafa*, while under the theorization of the early theologians it was closer to *adab* instead. He saw in Ḡurḡānī’s *Asrār* the roots of the philosophical “explicatory method” (*al-ṭarīqa al-taqrīriyya*) that led Arabic *bayān* toward its demise in the twelfth century.⁴⁸ Accordingly, he declares:

‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Ḡurḡānī was nothing but a *faylasūf* [Arabicized loan word from the Classical Greek *philosophos*] excellently commenting on and glossing Aristotle, while writing down, in the fifth century [after the Hiḡra ≈ eleventh CE], his book *Asrār al-Balāḡa* which is rightly considered the finest among the sources on Arabic *bayān*.⁴⁹

Ṭāhā Ḥusayn further attempts to bring out the Aristotelian influence on central thinkers in this tradition after the mid-ninth century in works such as *K. al-Šinā’atayn* of Abū Hilāl al-‘Askarī (d. ca. 1010) and *Naqd al-naṭr* (attributed at the time to Qudāma b. Ḡa’far), by uncovering in them fundamental elements borrowed from Aristotle’s *Rhetoric* and *Poetics*, as well as his logic more generally.⁵⁰ Following this path, Ḥusayn undertakes to revive a different set of sources, those directly or indirectly documenting the Greek influence on the so-called Arabic *bayān*, such as the above-mentioned *Naqd al-naṭr* and *Naqd al-šīr*.⁵¹ But above all, he set out to revive the Avicennian intellectual heritage. It was Avicenna’s “Arabicization” of Aristotle’s *Rhetoric*, according to Ḥusayn, that made this Aristotelian source available to Arabic thinkers and paved the way for the successful harmonization of the various elements of *bayān* at the hands of Ḡurḡānī.⁵² He thus focused his energy on supporting the gigantic project of the first critical edition of Avicenna’s *Šifā’*, including his *al-Ḥiṭāba* and *al-Šīr*, which represented the successful Arabicization of the Aristotelian *Rhetoric* and *Poetics* respectively. He was first and foremost the intellectual father of the scientific committee that carried out the project, the majority of whose members were among his students, later on financing the project in his function as Egypt’s minister of culture. This

48 Ḥusayn, *ibid.*, 11-2.

49 Ḥusayn, *ibid.*, 14.

50 Ḥusayn, *ibid.*, 19-28.

51 The pseudo-Qudāma’s *Naqd al-naṭr* turned out later to be *al-Burhān fī wuḡūh al-bayān* by Ibn Wahb al-Kātib (d. 947), see Ibn Wahb al-Kātib, *al-Burhān fī wuḡūh al-bayān*, ed. Ḥifnī Muḥammad Šaraf (Cairo: Maṭba’at al-risāla, 1969).

52 Ḥusayn, “Tamhīd fī l-bayān al-‘arabī,” 28.

narrative, which Ṭāhā Ḥusayn forcefully established through his writings and editorial works, led to the conclusion that:

[t]hroughout its developments, it [i.e., Arabic *bayān*] has been firmly connected firstly to Greek philosophy and secondly to Greek *bayān*. Thus, Aristotle is not only the first teacher of Muslims in *falsafa*, but, in addition to that, he is their first teacher in the science of *bayān*.⁵³

After ‘Abduh’s endeavor to Arabicize the science of *bayān* with Ḡurḡānī as its protagonist, Ṭāhā Ḥusayn reframed both the discipline and the protagonist as Greek dressed in Arabic clothing. Despite some attempts at moderating this radically Hellenized image of Ḡurḡānī, the Greek traces in this domain continued to enjoy the lion’s share of scholarly attention. Among later scholars who attempted such a moderating assessment was Ḥusayn’s younger contemporary, Muḥammad Ḥalafallāh Aḥmad (d. 1983). By putting the emphasis once again on *taste*, he wanted to restore the Arabic background to Ḡurḡānī’s project. As if corroborating ‘Abduh’s emphasis on *dawq* in Ḡurḡānī’s project, Ḥalafallāh sets about reconstructing what he calls the gustatory or aesthetic philosophy (*al-falsafa al-dawqiyya*) of Ḡurḡānī. He was aware, however, that this emphasis is in complete agreement with Ḥusayn’s emphasis on Greek influence.⁵⁴

Ḥalafallāh considers both works of Ḡurḡānī as constituting “a coherent theory of literature,” as the latter treats the “structural aspect of literary composition” while the former studies “the aesthetic side as it is exemplified in creative images (metaphors, tropes, comparisons, and the like).” He further describes the latter as dealing with “composition as a construction” and the former as a study on “compositions as a beautiful object to be appreciated and enjoyed.” In his study, however, Ḥalafallāh focuses on *Asrār*, interpreting Ḡurḡānī’s emphasis on the paramount importance of meaning (*ma’na*) in “literary criticism” as an emphasis on “its effect on the mind and soul of the reader.” Representing Ḡurḡānī as a Greek-inspired philosopher who was completely indebted to the Aristotelian tradition required zooming in on the *Asrār*. In this paradigm, the *Dalā’il* was always overshadowed by the former, since it made possible fewer connections and less correspondence to the Greek heritage. Consequently, Ḥalafallāh discerns that according to the “basic principle” behind all chief theoretical contributions of Ḡurḡānī, “the test of literary excellence is-or should be-the effect of creative images on the mind and soul of an appreciative reader.” By highlighting such examples, Ḥalafallāh aims to reveal the “psychological atmosphere” prevailing the whole work of Ḡurḡānī.⁵⁵

This psychological reading of Ḡurḡānī, which would lay the foundation for numerous future psychological treatments of this work, allows Ḥalafallāh to draw “comparisons of ‘Abd al-Qāhir’s ‘Secrets of Eloquence’ with Avicenna’s Arabic version of Aristotle’s ‘Poetics and

53 Ḥusayn, “Tamhīd fī l-bayān al-‘arabī,” 31: “innahu [sc. al-bayān al-‘arabī] kāna fī ḡamī‘ atwārihī waṭīq al-ṣīla bi-l-falsafa al-yūnāniyya awwalan wa-bi-l-bayān al-yūnānī aḥīran. Wa-īdan lā yakūnu Aristū al-mu‘allim al-awwal li-l-muslimīn fī l-falsafa waḥdahā, wa-lākin nahu ilā ḡānīb dālīka mu‘allimuhum al-awwal fī ‘ilm al-bayān.”

54 Muḥammad Ḥalafallāh Aḥmad, “Nazariyyat ‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Ḡurḡānī fī *Asrār al-balāḡa*,” *Maḡallat Kulliyat al-Ādāb, Ḡāmi‘at Fārūq al-Awwal* (1944), 2: 14-84, esp. 15.

55 Ḥalafallāh, “Nazariyyat ‘Abd al-Qāhir,” 81.

Rhetoric,” and to accordingly “infer that ‘Abd al-Qāhir must have studied that version and made use of it, especially in the section on diction and style.”⁵⁶ Thus, Ḥalafallāh turns to implement Ḥusayn’s view in locating Ğurġānī within the Hellenic paradigm with all its consequences. According to him, Ğurġānī’s achievement and self-declared aim in the two works is to “put Arabic literary criticism on a new and scientific basis.”⁵⁷ In Ḥalafallāh’s view, this represents Ğurġānī’s matchless success in reconciling gustatory literary thinking (*al-tafkīr al-adabī al-dawqī*) with a scientific philosophical approach (*al-manhaġ al-falsafī al-‘ilmī*), employing knowledge to discover the secrets of taste (*dawq*).⁵⁸ He thus attempts to show the modern relevance of Ğurġānī in the “application of psychological thought to the enlightenment of literary criticism.”⁵⁹ What Ḥalafallāh eventually accomplishes is to further enhance the psychological approach that Ḥusayn himself initiated in his dissertation from 1914.⁶⁰

Despite apparent disagreements, ‘Abduh, who (over)emphasizes taste in Ğurġānī’s project, Ḥusayn, who utterly denies Ğurġānī’s Arabic purity, and Ḥalafallāh, who consolidates the psychological reading of Ğurġānī, read this thinker and his works in ways that are fundamentally congruent and complementary, relying on the theoretical separation of intellect and imagination and on the polar opposition between philosophy/*falsafa* and literature/*bayān* and *adab*.⁶¹ This distinction, stemming from ancient Greece, first pervaded the Islamic world after its encounter with the Greek scientific heritage, which, far from being a random and superficial contact, consisted of a deep and programmatic engagement over a period of no less than two hundred years. This began in around the mid-eighth century in the heart of the Islamic world in the form of a Greco-Arabic translation movement, abundantly supported by the caliphs and the ruling elite of Baghdad.⁶² This encounter fundamentally affected intellectual life in the Islamic world. By and by, not only the above-mentioned distinction but numerous previously unknown theoretical distinctions and classifications, as conceived in the Greek context, were assimilated, partially or wholly, into the multifarious fields of knowledge in the Islamic tradition, including *bayān*.

However, beyond the shared conceptual context for the analysis of Ğurġānī’s scholarly output, Ḥusayn clearly stands out not only in the totality and universality of his denial of a purely Arabic *bayān*, let alone *falsafa*, but also in his endeavor to demonstrate the Greek

56 Ḥalafallāh, *ibid.*, 82.

57 Ḥalafallāh, *ibid.*, 80.

58 Ḥalafallāh, *ibid.*, 79.

59 Ḥalafallāh, *ibid.*, 82.

60 See Muḥammad Ḥalafallāh Aḥmad, *Min al-wiġha al-naḥsiyya fī dirāsāt al-adab wa-naqdih* (Cairo: Laġnat al-ta’līf wa-l-tarġama wa-l-našr, 1947).

61 For Ḥusayn’s distinction between the two domains, see Tāhā Ḥusayn, *Qādat al-fikr* (Cairo: Idārat al-hilāl, 1925), 14-5.

62 For an excellent study on this translation movement in its social, historical, political, and ideological context, see Dimitri Gutas, *Greek Thought, Arabic Culture: The Graeco-Arabic Translation Movement in Baghdad and Early ‘Abbasid Society (2nd–4th/5th–10th centuries)* (London and New York: Routledge, 1998); cf. id., “The Rebirth of Philosophy and the Translations into Arabic,” in *Philosophy in the Islamic World*, vol. 1: *8th–10th Centuries*, ed. Ulrich Rudolph, Rotraud Hansberger, and Peter Adamson, transl. by Rotraud Hansberger (Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2016), 95-142.

influence beyond the field of *falsafa* in *bayān* and *adab*: Arab Muslims were the disciples of the Greek Aristotle in both fields from the very beginning. Thus, Hellenization did not reach the Islamic world for the first time several hundred years after its emergence during the translation movement, but far earlier. Such a total Hellenization meant to serve as a way to transcend the divide between the East and the West.⁶³ “Poetry” was the foundation upon which both Greek and Arabic civilization were based, Ḥusayn declares, adding: “and we can say nothing else but poetry; Arabs and Greeks were entirely similar in this respect.”⁶⁴ The only difference between Greeks and Arabs at this pre-civilizational stage was that the impact of the latter was far greater than the former and extended—through Romans and Arabs—to the modern day.⁶⁵ In the philosophical sphere, rationality had two manifestations: one Greek and the other Eastern. “Pure Greek rationality” was, however, victorious over “Eastern” rationality, and it “dominates human life up to our day and will continue to do so until the end of time.”⁶⁶ By demonstrating the Hellenization of both philosophical and poetical components of the cultural identity of the Islamic world, Ḥusayn must have aspired to dispel, once and for all, all doubts concerning the aptitude of the Islamic world for modernization.

Instead of being seen as a fully-fledged Hellenophile proponent of Greek or Western thought at the expense of Arabic or Eastern thought, Ḥusayn is to be seen as an intellectual who attempted to go beyond such distinctions, by fundamentally unifying the East and the West. Indeed, in addition to Homer, Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle, Ḥusayn lists Alexander the Great among the supreme leaders of thought, due not to his military conquests, but rather to his intellectual achievements. According to Ḥusayn, it was thanks to Alexander that

the rational distinctions between [Easterners and Westerners] were resolved [...]. He is the one who brought the East and the West close together and blended the Eastern rationality with the Western rationality.⁶⁷

In this sense, Ḥusayn attempts to sketch a global history of *bayān* that points towards the common cultural identity of the East (i.e., the Arabic/Islamic world) and the West (i.e., Europe). Long before Ḥusayn, Carl Heinrich Becker (d. 1933), the renowned German orientalist and mentor of Hellmut Ritter, had tried to escape what we now call Eurocentrism by means of a similar approach that emphasizes Hellenism, itself a co-product of different ancient civilizations, as the only explanation for considering the Islamic world a single, unitary civilization (*Einheitszivilisation*), confidently declaring: “ohne Alexander den Großen keine islamische Zivilisation.”⁶⁸

63 Likewise concerning his homeland, he divorces the Egyptian intellect from Eastern intellect to highlight its closeness and interaction with the Greek intellect, thus declaring Egypt a Western country. See Tāhā Ḥusayn, *Mustaqbal al-ṭāqāfa fī Miṣr* (Cairo: Dār al-maʿārif, 1938), esp. 21-4 (=chap. 3).

64 Ḥusayn, *Qādat al-fikr*, 6.

65 Ḥusayn, *ibid.*, 7-8.

66 Ḥusayn, *ibid.*, 22-3.

67 Ḥusayn, *ibid.*, 102.

68 Carl Heinrich Becker, “Der Islam als Problem,” *Der Islam*, 1.1 (1910); cf. Josef van Ess, *Im Halbschatten: Der Orientalist Hellmut Ritter (1892-1971)* (Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2013), 85-6 and the reference to Ritter’s letter there to Becker, where he expresses his doubts concerning this topic (van Ess, *Im Halbschatten*, 85, n. 58). As van Ess puts it elsewhere: “Becker... wanted to integrate the Near

2. Bayān in Europe

2.1. Learning Arabic to Dethrone Arabic

Wir sehen also die Hauptgründe dafür, daß die Aufnahme des griechischen Erbes im Orient zwar nicht minder tiefgreifend und umgestaltend war als bei den Römern, aber von einer ins Innerste hinabreichenden, nicht anders als tragisch zu nennenden Unfruchtbarkeit. [Becker's student Hans Heinrich Schaeder, *Der Mensch in Orient und Okzident*]⁶⁹

In Europe, Ğurġānī first attracted scholarly attention as a grammarian, that is, as an expert in the domain of Arabic grammar or *naḥw*. His fame as a theoretician in the domain of *bayān* followed a couple of centuries later. Corresponding to Europe's early endeavors to attain mastery of the Arabic language within the context of international cultural and religious politics, it was the grammarian Ğurġānī who engaged early modern European scholars thanks to his treatise on proper grammar, *Mi'at āmil* ("One Hundred Agents," also known as *al-'Awāmil al-mi'a*). This work proved particularly handy as a highly systematic and concise toolbox and was a perfect complement to another widely used grammatical work in Europe, *al-Āġurrūmiyya* by Ibn Āġurrūm (d. 1323). Ğurġānī's clear and jargon-free style in this work facilitated a smooth introduction to Arabic grammar for Western scholars, who were well versed in Latin grammar but unfamiliar with the syntactic and morphological terminology of Arabic grammar. Two scholars showed particular interest in this work at the turn of the seventeenth century: Giovanni Battista Raimondi (d. 1614) and Thomas Erpenius (d. 1624).

The former was an enthusiast linguist directing the scholarly programs, as well as the practical works, of the Medici Oriental Press (the *Typographia Medicea*), which granted him access to a large collection of oriental manuscripts.⁷⁰ This Catholic press had been founded in Rome with Pope Gregory XIII's support in 1584 and, under his direction, sought to meet missionary and commercial needs through the publication of scholarly classics, grammars, dictionaries, holy scriptures, and a polyglot Bible in the languages of the Middle East, as well as selling these books throughout the world. Raimondi left behind an unpublished, partial,

East into the Western world... He saw a common root, and therefore a common ground for hermeneutic understanding: the Greek heritage." Josef van Ess, "From Wellhausen to Becker: The Emergence of *Kulturgeschichte* in Islamic Studies," in: *Kleine Schriften* (Leiden: Brill, 2018), 25.

69 Hans Heinrich Schaeder, *Der Mensch in Orient und Okzident: Grundzüge einer eurasiatischen Geschichte*, ed. Grete Schaeder (Munich: Piper, 1960), 116: "Thus, we observe the primary reasons why the reception of the Greek heritage in the Orient, while no less profound and transformative as that among the Romans, suffered from a profound barrenness that extended deep into its core, which cannot but be called other than tragic."

70 Guglielmo E. Saltini, "Della Stamperia Orientale Medicea e di Giovan Battista Raimondi," *Giornale Storico degli Archivi Toscani*, IV (1860), 257-96. For a collection of studies on the role of the Medici Grand Dukes in the East-West relations in the early modern age see, Marta Caroscio and Maurizio Arfaioi (eds.), *The Grand Ducal Medici and the Levant, Material Culture, Diplomacy, and Imagery in the Early Modern Mediterranean* (London: Harvey Miller Publishers, 2016). For a more general history of the major library collections in the languages of those countries with Islam as the principal religion, mainly in the Middle East, in western European countries (the United Kingdom, France, Italy, Germany, the Netherlands, Spain and Denmark) and North America, see Stephan Roman, *The Development of Islamic Library Collections in Western Europe and North America* (London and New York: Mansell, 1990).

interlineal translation of Ğurġānī's *Mi'at 'āmil*.⁷¹ Thomas Erpenius was the first professor of Arabic in the Dutch Republic, at Leiden University, and “translated and edited numerous basic Arabic texts especially for the purpose of teaching and for the Protestant missions.”⁷² Based on a unique manuscript that he probably acquired during his post-studies travels (ca. 1608) to the main centers of oriental studies in Europe,⁷³ he published a Latin translation of Ğurġānī's *Mi'at 'āmil* in Leiden in 1617 under the title *Grammatica Arabica*⁷⁴ together in a single volume with *al-Āġurrūmiyya*.

As Erpenius reports, Raimondi intended to publish the book himself along with a Latin translation, “however, prevented by death, he did not publish it.”⁷⁵ Despite his great respect for Raimondi, Erpenius apparently saw himself as even more qualified to carry out such a task.⁷⁶ In general, Raimondi shows more interest in and seems more preoccupied with the Persian language.⁷⁷ His deep fascination with this language is manifest in his ranking of beautiful languages, in which Persian stands above all others, followed by Greek and then Arabic, particularly thanks to its expressive capacity of poetic concepts.⁷⁸ Even though Arabic only ranked third on Raimondi's list of beautiful languages, his partial translation of Ğurġānī's book shows that he had a better grasp of the contents of the book than Erpenius. As Jones shows, the latter fails to grasp fundamental syntactic concepts in his translation. However, deciphering a work on Arabic grammar, even one as uncomplicated as that of Ğurġānī, posed a challenge to European scholars who were limited in their Arabic learning to the sources available to them in Europe.⁷⁹ Erpenius completed the unfinished task of

71 Jones' study of the development of Arabic studies in early modern Europe contains a detailed study of Raimondi's interlineal translation of Ğurġānī's *Mi'at 'āmil*. See Robert Jones, *Learning Arabic in Renaissance Europe (1505-1624)* (Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2020), 227-35.

72 Arnoud Vrolijk and Richard van Leeuwen, *Arabic Studies in the Netherlands: A Short History in Portraits, 1580-1950*, transl. by Alastair Hamilton (Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2013), 33.

73 For Erpenius, see Vrolijk and van Leeuwen, *Arabic Studies in the Netherlands*, 29-40.

74 Thomas Erpenius, *Grammatica Arabica dicta Gjarumia & Libellus Centum Regentium cum versione Latina & Commentariis* (Leiden: Typographia Erpeniana Linguarum Orientalium, 1617).

75 Erpenius, *Grammatica Arabica*, 1617, A4r: “Promisit aliquando hoc opusculum in suo /taṣrīf/ Romae excuse, Doctissimus Io. Baptista Raimundus, sed morte praeventus non dedit.” Translation from Jones, *Learning Arabic in Renaissance Europe*, 230.

76 For Erpenius' evaluation of Raimondi's work on Arabic grammar see Jones, *Learning Arabic in Renaissance Europe*, 229-35.

77 On Raimondi's Persian studies, see Angelo Michele Piemontese, “The Emergence of Persian Grammar and Lexicography in Rome,” *Rivista degli studi orientali*, 83.1/4 (2010): 399-415.

78 Jones, *Learning Arabic in Renaissance Europe*, 274.

79 None of the two scholars apparently made it to the Middle East in person. Farina shows in her linguistic and text-critical analysis of an account of a journey by land from Hurmuz to Venice dated to 1575 and attributed by nineteenth century Italian historiography to Giovanni Battista Raimondi, that the latter did not make such a travel, nor did he compose the account, but merely copied the document in the context of the preparation of a mission to Egypt and Persia of Giovanni Battista Vecchiotti (1552-1619), who left to Alexandria in 1584, as a papal envoy; see Margherita Farina, “Giovanni Battista Raimondi's Travel in the Middle East: A Case of Sixteenth-Century Portuguese-Italian Interference,” *Oriente Moderno*, 98.1 (2018), 52-72; cf. Roberto Almagià, *Giovan Battista e Gerolamo Vecchiotti, viaggiatori in Oriente* (Rome: Accademia nazionale dei Lincei, 1956). The brothers Giovanni Battista and Gerolamo Vecchiotti collected many important oriental manuscripts during their diplomatic and scientific missions in Egypt,

translating Ğurġānī's book after Raimondi's death. In his translation, he innovatively adopted the form and terminology of Latin grammars familiar to the students of Arabic in Europe, in order to provide them with a suitable textbook that was to replace similar earlier works and remain the standard reference work until the early nineteenth century.⁸⁰

Besides the desire for knowledge, numerous other motivations played a role in the scholarly activities of learned men such as Erpenius and Raimondi. The agenda of the Catholic Raimondi, for instance, corresponded to the objectives of Pope Gregory XIII, namely supporting the teaching of foreign languages to “nurture and discipline the dogmas of the Catholic faith.”⁸¹ This was, in turn, a step in the struggle of the Catholic Church to win over the Arab Christians to the bishop of Rome, as well as the re-Christianization of some Muslim lands and convert Christians.⁸² The Protestant Erpenius enumerated various motivations for studying the Arabic language in a lecture in 1620 to the students at the University of Leiden, including the motivations touching on theology and polemics:

Those of you who are candidates in Sacred Theology, consider what it would be to learn this language without the help of which your Sacred Language (and in my judgement you do not deserve to call it yours unless you lay claim to and acquire Arabic) cannot be fully and perfectly understood, or the impious doctrines of the Muhammadans be examined and beneficially refuted.⁸³

The time of the Crusades was over, and political, economic, or religious objectives of this kind motivated the engagement with oriental languages in general and with Arabic in particular, even though they did not distort the content of Ğurġānī's work. On the contrary, one can safely assume that it remained intact. This was mainly due to the conventional

Syria, Armenia, Persia, and India (1584-1608), at first as envoys of Pope Gregory XIII. During these travels, Giovanni Battista Vecchiotti learned Persian together with Hebrew from native teachers in Persia and later laid the foundation for the study of Judeo-Persian literature.

80 ‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Ğurġānī, *Grammatica arabica*, transl. by Thomas Erpenius (Leiden: n.p., 1617).

81 Saltini, “Della stamperia orientale medicea e di Giovan Battista Raimondi,” 259.

82 Looking further back, one could see this as a belated practical step toward realizing the pertinent decree of the Council of Vienne (1311-1312). In this Council the Catholic Church states clearly that “We desire earnestly that holy church should be well supplied with catholic scholars acquainted with the languages most in use by unbelievers. These scholars should know how to train unbelievers in the Christian way of life, and to make them members of the Christian body through instruction in the faith and reception of sacred baptism.” It, thus, calls for establishing schools for Arabic, among other languages, at Paris, Oxford, Bologna and Salamanca. The aim, as the document reveals, was to produce experts who “shall direct the schools, make faithful translations of books from these languages into Latin, and teach others those languages with all earnestness, passing on a skillful use of the language, so that after such instruction these others may, God inspiring, produce the harvest hoped for, propagating the saving faith among the heathen peoples.” See Council of Vienne (1311-1312), in *Papal Encyclicals Online*, consulted online 17.02.2022, via <https://www.papalencyclicals.net/councils/ecum15.htm>, decree no. 24. In practice, this decree was not consequential; c.f. Karl H. Dannenfeldt, “The Renaissance Humanists and the Knowledge of Arabic,” *Studies in the Renaissance*, 2 (1955), 96-117, esp. 97-8.

83 From the English translation of Erpenius' Latin oration. See Robert Jones, “Thomas Erpenius (1584–1624) on the Value of the Arabic Language,” *Manuscripts of the Middle East*, 1 (1986), 22.

character of the science it contained, which did not leave any room for interpretation—at least, not at this early stage of Arabic studies in Europe.⁸⁴

However, there was no possibility to study the Arabic language for its own sake in this highly charged context. This strand of scholarship on the grammatical heritage of Ğurġānī had no interest in the author of the work, although it was repeatedly translated, let alone in his other intellectual profile as a theorist in the field of *bayān*. Erpenius did not even care to know the name of the author of the work he was translating.⁸⁵ Later translators did not do any better. Ğurġānī’s work simply served as a useful instrument. Furthermore, one can also discern in this context a certain predilection for Persian over other languages of the Middle East, one that aligned with papal politics at the time, which sought to establish an alliance with Safavid Persia to face the Ottoman empire and to favor the activities of Catholic missionaries. Such issues conferred on the study of Persian more direct and practical urgency as compared to other oriental languages, including Arabic.⁸⁶

When the same text by Ğurġānī was translated again at the turn of the nineteenth century, this time into English, Europeans with an interest in Arabic were no longer confined within the boundaries of Europe, but were rather present all over the Middle East, this time not (only) in search of knowledge, but above all as an exercise of power and political dominance. Furthermore, during the two intervening centuries, the conceptual context had completely changed, and a narrative of the dominance of the Greek culture in all the traditions that came into contact with it had become established, along with all the ensuing theoretical misconceptions. Abraham Lockett, the English translator of Ğurġānī’s work in 1814,⁸⁷ still knowing “little or nothing”⁸⁸ about its author, had no doubt—despite his uncertainty concerning the source of his judgment—when considering the achievements of not only Ğurġānī, but Arab grammarians more generally, that

the merit of originality must be transferred to the Stagyrīte, whose dialectics, if I am not much mistaken, will be found to contain the most remarkable facts that distinguish the philosophical grammar of the Arabs.⁸⁹

In a parallel line of scholarship, men of learning in Europe extended their scholarly attention from Arabic language to Arabic literature. This shift can be seen as the further development of the struggle to acquire perfect knowledge of this language by mastering its highest literary

84 Cf. Abraham Lockett, “Preface,” in: *The Mi, ut Āmil, and Šurḥoo Mi, ut Āmil; Two Elementary Treatises on Arabic Syntax*, transl. by Abraham Lockett (Calcutta: The Hindoostanee Press, 1814), i-xxv.

85 Erpenius, *Grammatica Arabica*, A4r.

86 See the introductory section of Herbert Chick’s detailed chronicles, in Herbert Chick, *A Chronicle of the Carmelites in Persia and the Papal Mission of the XVIIth and XVIIIth Centuries* (London: Eyre & Spottiswoode, 1939¹), 1: 3-65.

87 ‘Abd al-Qāhir al-Ğurġānī, *The Mi, ut Āmil, and Šurḥoo Mi, ut Āmil; Two Elementary Treatises on Arabic Syntax*, transl. by Abraham Lockett (Calcutta: The Hindoostanee Press, 1814).

88 Ğurġānī, *The Mi, ut Āmil*, xv.

89 Ğurġānī, *ibid.*, viii-ix.

form, namely poetry.⁹⁰ Arabic literature also offered the most promising path to knowledge of the character of the Arabs, especially in the absence of direct contact with them. This line of scholarship, however, chose a path towards Arabic literature which went through Persian literature. Around the time when Friedrich Schlegel (d. 1829) and later Franz Bopp (d. 1867) were laying the philological foundations for constructing the Aryan man, German orientalists gave pride of place to Persian literature among the literary traditions of the “nations of the orient.”⁹¹ Hence, the Persian literary tradition, despite its intellectual debt to the earlier Arabic tradition, constituted their primary interest and, as a result, their (anachronistic) commencement point for the analysis of the literary tradition of the Arabs. What justified this preference was merely the racial affinity of the Persian and German peoples, whose languages not only had the same origins, but also a similar fate in being elaborated through “Rhetorik und Poesie.”⁹²

2.2. Germanizing the *Šayḥ* to Civilize the Islamic World

Hellmut Ritter’s initial interest in Ğurġānī was no exception in this context. He came to engage with Ğurġānī’s *Asrār* during his endeavors to bring out what he saw as the main characteristic of the Persian poetry of Niẓāmī (d. 1209), namely the aesthetic function of the metaphorical expression. Nonetheless, Ritter was one of the first scholars to highlight the preposterousness of studying Neo-Persian literature independently and without any linkage to Arabic literary history. In this regard, he found Ğurġānī’s discussions of verses from the Abbasid Arabic poets, such as Ibn al-Mu‘tazz and Ibn al-Rūmī (d. 896), in his *Asrār* to exhibit, from an aesthetic perspective, the same peculiarity that he was seeking in Niẓāmī.⁹³ After all, Ğurġānī, too, was “ein Perser” and remained far removed from the Arabic context,

90 Silvestre de Sacy, for instance, argued for the utility of the study of Arabic against Reiske who disapproved of it; see, for instance, Antoine Isaac Silvestre de Sacy, *De l'utilité de l'étude de la poésie arabe* (Paris: Librairie Orientale, 1826), 10.

91 Schlegel had argued in his *Über die Sprache und Weisheit der Indier*, that “[d]as alte indische Sanskrito [...] hat die größte Verwandtschaft mit der römischen und griechischen so wie mit der germanischen und persischen Sprache,” and the later *Über das Conjugationssystem der Sanskritsprache* of Bopp came to be known as one of the founding building blocks of comparative historical linguistics. See respectively, Friedrich von Schlegel, *Ueber die Sprache und Weisheit der Indier* (Heidelberg: Mohr und Zimmer, 1808), 1; Franz Bopp, *Über das Conjugationssystem der Sanskritsprache: in Vergleichung mit jenem der griechischen, lateinischen, persischen und germanischen Sprache; nebst Episoden des Ramajan und Mahabharat und einigen Abschnitten aus den Vedas* (Frankfurt am Main: Andreäische Buchhandlung, 1816).

92 Joseph von Hammer-Purgstall, *Geschichte der schönen Redekünste Persiens mit einer Blütenlese persischer Dichter aus zweyhundert persischen Dichtern* (Wien: Heubner und Volke, 1818), VIII: “Durch gründliches Sprachstudium ist die nächste Verwandtschaft der persischen und deutschen Sprache schon längst außer Zweifel gesetzt, und der bekannte Vers Seneca’s bewahrt, der die Perser vom Orus und Arares an die Elbe und an den Rhein versetzt. Wenn die Geschichte der persischen schönen Litteratur sich in der europäischen überhaupt einen freundlichen Empfang versprechen darf, um wie günstiger muß derselbe nicht im deutschen Vaterlande ausfallen, da beyde Sprachen nicht nur gleichen Ursprungs, sondern auch in ihrer Ausbildung durch Rhetorik und Poesie eines ähnlichen Schicksals theilhaftig geworden, von der ältesten Zeit an bis ans die neueste.”

93 See Hellmut Ritter, *Über die Bildsprache Niẓāmīs* (Berlin, Leipzig: De Gruyter, 1927), 2; id., “Einführung,” in: *Die Geheimnisse der Wortkunst (Asrār al-balāġa)*, transl. by Hellmut Ritter (Wiesbaden: Franz Steiner, 1959), 1-2.

as he “hat seine heimat⁹⁴ niemals verlassen und hat daher bei keinem der berühmten meister der arabischen sprachgelehrsamkeit studiert.”⁹⁵

However, this indirect interest in Ğurġānī at this stage developed into Ritter’s lifelong fascination, giving rise to a significant scholarly output that marks a turning point in scholarship on Ğurġānī in Europe. Like the Egyptian reformist ‘Abduh, Ritter represents in his own context the first direct scholarly engagement with the work of Ğurġānī himself, in contradistinction to the sporadic and often indirect treatment of his intellectual heritage among earlier European scholars. Up to that point, to study Ğurġānī, in both the fields of *naḥw* and *bayān*, European scholars were forced to go through the commentary traditions on his works stemming from later centuries, which were partly imbued with Greek intellectual heritage.⁹⁶ This presence of Ğurġānī in the shadow of his commentators went back a good three centuries in Europe, before Ritter stumbled upon his works during his explorations in Persian literature. Against this backdrop, Ritter’s decision to edit and translate Ğurġānī’s own work into German represents a departure from this dominant anachronistic praxis.

In 1959, Ritter finalized and published his translation of Ğurġānī’s *Asrār*, the first—and so far only complete—translation into a European language, after more than three decades of disconnected but persistent work (he had finished the full translation already in 1925).⁹⁷ In the introduction to his edition, Ritter, following in the footsteps of Ḥalafallāh, opposes Ṭāhā Ḥusayn’s claim, cited earlier, concerning the fundamental indebtedness of Arabic *bayān* and *adab* to its presumed Greek predecessors. Ritter argues that, to the contrary, the development of Arabic poetry in terms of formal elements, such as “simile, metaphor, antithesis, paronomasia, ploke, [etc.],”⁹⁸ can hardly be imagined as having developed among the Arabs under Greek influence, especially that of Aristotle’s *Rhetoric* and *Poetics*. These two Aristotelian works were “very little to the taste of the Arabs,” as Ritter notes.⁹⁹ Highlighting the lack of textual evidence for Ḥusayn’s thesis concerning “the Hellenization of the Arabian world,” Ritter emphasizes that authors in this tradition seem, in fact, to fall back exclusively on Arabic sources.¹⁰⁰ In his introduction to the German translation of the same work some years later, he underscores once again that Ğurġānī’s *Asrār* and its discussions on various

94 Here, and throughout, I have retained the original orthography of German sources, as it is no impediment to comprehension.

95 In addition, Ğurġānī is introduced as having studied with no well-known master of Arabic grammar on the ground that he supposedly never left his hometown Ğurġān—his only master being thus the student and sister’s son of Abū ‘Alī al-Fārisī (d. 987) (Ritter, *Geheimnisse*, 5-6). Though the claim might be true, there seems to be some textual evidence against the justification. Al-Bāḥarī seems to indicate in the entry on Ğurġānī in his *Dumya* that the latter had indeed left his hometown going on a pilgrimage to Mekka: “wa-lastu fī-mā fātānī min karīm mušāhadatihi... illā ka-man wadda’a l-mā’ wa-l-ḥuḍra... falamā ḥallafa ḥādīhi l-ḥiṭa’ wa-šārafa min bayni sā’ir al-ḥiṭa’ al-ka’ba...” See ‘Alī b. al-Ḥasan b. ‘Alī b. Abī l-Ṭayyib al-Bāḥarī, *Dumyat al-qasr wa-‘aṣrat ahl al-‘aṣr*, ed. Muḥammad al-Tūnaġī (Beirut: Dār al-ġīl, 1993), 1: 578.

96 See, for instance, August Ferdinand Mehren, *Die Rhetorik der Araber nach den wichtigsten Quellen dargestellt* (Kopenhagen: Otto Schwartz, 1853).

97 Ritter, “Einführung,” 1.

98 Ritter, “Introduction,” 2.

99 Ritter, *Bildsprache*, 4.

100 Ritter, “Introduction,” 3-4.

“rhetorical” issues contain “so viel eigenartiges und originelles” and also “spezifisches ‘arabisches’.”¹⁰¹

By denying the reducibility of *bayān* to some Greek ancestor, Ritter disagrees with Husayn concerning his Hellenization thesis and subsequently his critique of the authenticity of the *Ġāhiliyya*. In this disagreement, he goes even further than Ḥalafallāh. However, despite his comprehensive denial of Greek influence in the domain of *bayān*, Ritter takes over the emphasis on taste and goes on to develop his own understanding of the work within the paradigm of the polarity between philosophy and poetry. Between these two domains, he saw the originality of the Arabs in poetry. As for philosophy, Ritter joins numerous orientalisists of the period in thinking that “Ġazālī’s *Tahāfut* stellt einen Schlußpunkt dar, den Schlußpunkt unter die philosophische[n] Erörterungen im Islam.”¹⁰² Evidence shows that he relied on this narrative both a few years before and a couple of years after publishing his own edition of Ġurġānī’s *Asrār al-balāġa*, half a century after ‘Abduh’s edition.¹⁰³ In the same spirit, he finds the field of *bayān* void of philosophical competence, where the “judgements passed are often subjective and arbitrary and sometimes unsupported.”¹⁰⁴

Following Spuler, from whom he probably took over the thesis concerning the death of philosophy in the Islamic world after Ġazālī,¹⁰⁵ Ritter makes a distinction between Christianity and Islam in terms of their relation to Hellenism. He writes:

Bei der Entstehung des Christentums hat schon der Hellenismus mitgewirkt. Das Christentum ist dem Ursprunge nach eine orientalische, semitische Religion, ist aber erst zu dem geworden, was es ist, durch den Einfluß der hellenistischen Kultur... Die Grundlagen der islamischen Kultur waren schon vor dem Beginn des hellenischen Einflusses gelegt; eine islamische Dogmatik war auch ohne eine völlige Durchtränkung mit hellenistischem Geiste denkbar, anders als im Christentum.¹⁰⁶

101 Ritter, “Einführung,” 2-3.

102 Hellmut Ritter, “Hat die religiöse Orthodoxie einen Einfluss auf die Dekadenz des Islams ausgeübt?,” in *Klassizismus und Kulturverfall*, ed. Gustav E. von Grunebaum and Willy Hartner (Frankfurt am Main: Vittorio Klostermann, 1956), 121. See also Hellmut Ritter, “L’orthodoxie a-t-elle une part dans la décadence?,” in *Classicisme et déclin culturel dans l’histoire de l’Islam : Actes du symposium international d’histoire de la civilisation musulmane (Bordeaux 25-29 Juin 1956)*, ed. Gustav E. von Grunebaum and Robert Brunschvig (Paris: Maisonneuve et Larose, 1977), 168: “Ainsi finit non seulement la vie personnelle de Ghazālī, mais aussi l’histoire spirituelle de l’Islam au Moyen âge en général. Le *Tahāfut* de Ghazālī est un point final, le point final aux débats philosophiques originaux dans l’Islam.”

103 In both cases, he was delivering lectures concerning the cultural decline and decadence of Muslim civilization. See Gustav E. von Grunebaum and Willy Hartner (eds.), *Klassizismus und Kulturverfall* (Frankfurt am Main: Vittorio Klostermann, 1956), 1-2.

104 Ritter, “Introduction,” 5.

105 In a more nuanced defense of this thesis, Spuler writes: “Die offizielle Anerkennung der Mystik hat zusammen mit al-Ghazzālī’s ‚Destructio philosophorum‘ (*Tahāfut al-falāsifa*) für den Osten des Islams weithin sichtbar den Schlußpunkt unter diese Periode der philosophischen Erörterungen gesetzt.” See Bertold Spuler, “Hellenistisches Denken im Islam,” *Saeculum*, 5 (1954), 188.

106 Ritter, “Religiöse Orthodoxie,” 129-30.

It was for this reason that Hellenism met a tragic end in the Islamic world, in contrast to its splendid development in the Christian West. As Ritter writes: “Daher sei das hellenistische Gedankengut allmählich, wenn auch nicht völlig, aus dem Islam ausgeschieden worden.”¹⁰⁷

However, unlike numerous other affiliates of Becker who followed his analysis of Islamic “civilization,” Ritter did not conclude the impossibility of a renaissance in the Islamic world. On the contrary, he attempted to devise a new concept of renaissance and humanism, falling back not on the ancient Greek, but rather on the pre-Islamic Arabic literary tradition, thus demonstrating the possibility of a renaissance in the Islamic world that was natural to it. He wrote:

Die Renaissance in Italien war ein Zurückgreifen auf die eigene heidnische, aber kulturell hoch entwickelte Vergangenheit. Auch die Araber hatten eine heidnische Vergangenheit, auf die sie zurückgreifen konnten: die *Ġāhiliyya*. Was enthielt diese Vergangenheit an kulturellen Elementen? Die Poesie. Sie ist das einzige Kulturelement Altarabiens, das weiter gewirkt hat. Man sieht auch im Zeitalter der großen Grammatiker, wie sich eine Art humanistisches Interesse an der altarabischen Poesie entwickelt.¹⁰⁸

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Poetry was the idiosyncratic trait of the Arabs in contrast to other nations. In this sense, Ritter falls back on longstanding presuppositions concerning the nature of the Arabs among orientalist, within the paradigm of the polarity between literature and philosophy. His representation of Arabs as masters of poetry and natural-born lords of imagination is one side of a coin whose other side is the utter rejection of their intellectual adeptness, as indicated above. In this light, he does not hesitate to locate Ġurġānī in a tradition of *literary criticism*. It was commonly assumed by the time Ritter published his critical edition of *Asrār* that Arabs were distinguished by their “remarkable talent for literary art.”¹⁰⁹ His emphasis at the beginning of the introduction to his edition of Ġurġānī’s *Asrār* on the prominent aptitude of the ancient Arabs and the Bedouins “for literary art,” clearly connects him with scholars in his own tradition.

A century earlier, for instance, August Ferdinand Mehren held the same view concerning the linguistic maturity of the Arabs in his *Die Rhetorik der Araber* (published in 1853) writing:

Diese im Verhältnisse zu dem Standpuncte der übrigen Cultur so frühe Ausbildung der Sprache liegt in der geistigen Natur der Araber tief begründet, weswegen bei ihnen diese als der erste Gegenstand der wissenschaftlichen Studien in einem weit höheren Grade als bei anderen Nationen hervortritt, und die Bestrebung, sie rein von allen fremden Einmischungen zu halten, von Alters her sich geltend machte.¹¹⁰

107 Ritter, *ibid.*

108 Ritter, *ibid.*, 130.

109 Ritter, “Introduction,” 1.

110 Mehren, *Die Rhetorik der Araber*, 1.

This discipline is, according to such views, profoundly grounded in the *geistige Natur* of the Arabs. Ritter's emphasis on taste, in line with 'Abduh, approximates this position, leading him to understand *bayān* as poetics. He describes the literary art of the Arabs as "rich, though one-sided." By "one-sided," he means that it "consists mainly of poetry." Thus, he narrows down the scope of intellectual engagement with the Islamic world, even in its rudimentary stages, to the domain of poetry and poetic criticism.¹¹¹

Against this background, Ritter gives a brief sketch of the development of this line of intellectual pursuit in the Islamic world up to, more or less, the tenth century, when "eloquence (*balāgha*)" and "aesthetic criticism" took center stage at the hands of scholars such as Abū Hilāl al-'Askarī (d. 1005), Ibn Rašīq (d. ca. 1071), Abū l-Qāsim al-Āmidī (d. 980), and Abū l-Ḥasan 'Alī al-Ġurġānī (d. 1002), authors who are considered to be among Ġurġānī's main sources. Up to this point, according to Ritter, the "standards according to which the Arabian critics rated poetry" were elaborately worked out, manifesting "[a]n astonishing connoisseurship [...] a vast knowledge of poetic works and a highly developed taste." The emphasis on "taste" as the main cognitive source in this tradition of "literary" or "aesthetic criticism" and "poetry" as the subject matter of this type of study is present throughout the introduction.

Ritter perceives the general aim of Ġurġānī's project, its significance, and its place within sciences against the background of such a reductionist conception of the scope of *Asrār*. He introduces this work as a "quite new approach" in the tradition he sketches, which, together with Ġurġānī's other work, *Dalā'il*, "have become in the sphere of *poetic* and *rhetoric* basically important for subsequent generations." According to him, even though the announced purpose of the latter work is "to prove that the rhetorical style of the Koran is inimitable [...]" in reality it is a very subtle theory of syntactic stylistics." He considers this work "an important supplement to the theory of syntax as presented by Sībawayh and his successors." In sum, he emphasizes that "[t]hese two books revolutionized the studies of *rhetoric* in the East."¹¹² Furthermore, he published his translation of Ġurġānī's *Asrār* six years after his edition, considering it "eine psychologische Begründung ästhetischer Werturteile über Poesie."¹¹³

Thus, on the one hand, Ritter readily falls back on the psychological approach, initiated by Ṭāhā Ḥusayn and further elaborated by Ḥalafallāh, within the sphere of *dawq* or taste to analyze Ġurġānī's intellectual heritage in "the sphere of poetic and rhetoric." For him, Ġurġānī's whole project is consequently nothing but "stylistics."¹¹⁴ On the other hand, he uses a conceptual apparatus that closely corresponds to the tradition of European scholarship on Arabic literature, assuming a natural link between this discipline and the Arabs. It vividly reminds us, for instance, of Becker's mentor, the Hungarian orientalist Ignác Goldziher (d. 1921), who employs a similar constellation of concepts in his *Abhandlungen zur arabischen Philologie*, published in 1896, to analyze thinkers such as Ibn Rašīq and Ibn al-Aṭīr as "ästhetischer Kritiker," "Stilisten," or "belletristische Schriftsteller" in the "Gebiete der

111 Ritter, "Introduction," 1.

112 Ritter, *ibid.*, 6.

113 Ritter, *ibid.*, 1.

114 Ritter, *ibid.*, 1.

Poetik,” who with their “ästhetische Betrachtungsweise” represent a significant moment in the history of discussions on poetry.¹¹⁵ In both cases, he sees *bayān* in the context of the polarity between imagination and intellection, as a discipline opposed to *falsafa*.

Thus, Ritter seems to be closer to ‘Abduh, who saw the decadence of the Islamic world in its being de-Arabicized and advocated for its re-Arabicization, than to Ḥusayn, who saw the decadence of the Islamic world in its de-Hellenization and wanted to re-Hellenize it. For Ritter, the Islamic world had an Arabic origin, in line with ‘Abduh’s view, and it had been de-Hellenized, in accordance with Ḥusayn’s understanding. However, having witnessed the Second World War and the nefarious consequences of technological and scientific progress in the West, he was not so sure whether the same path taken in the West would lead to renewed flourishing in the East. Acknowledging that the Islamic world rejected the alien Greek element from its body after a few centuries, he sought to find the originality of the Arabs in the field of imagination and taste, in *bayān*, thanks to which Arabs could be formed into a unified civilization developing towards a flourishing of its own, without joining the West in progress that was taking it into an unknown future, probably to “self-destruction.”¹¹⁶

Concluding Words

For each speech that you find worthy of praise and [for] each utterance that you consider excellent, your judgement must rest on a cognizable reason and an intelligible cause. Furthermore, we must have a way for expressing that and a proof for the correctness of our claim. [Ġurġānī, *Dalā’il*, 41]

Considering ‘Abduh and Ritter in their engagement with Ġurġānī shows how inextricably the historiographical fates of *bayān* and *falsafa* are intertwined. The latter has constituted the implicit background against which the former has been conceptualized and studied. From the very beginning, when the theoretical engagement with the language of the Quran and poetry gradually became recognizably systematic during the first few centuries of Islam and formed into the science of *bayān*, it was contrasted with the intellectual tradition of *falsafa*. To *falsafa* belonged the sphere of intellect, the domain of truth and rational proof and, in one word, rationality. *Bayān*, in contrast, was assigned to the domain of imagination revolving around imitation and taste and, in effect, restrained within the bounds of irrationality. Due to this close link, the unexamined assumptions and prejudices concerning *falsafa* in the Islamic world have been consequential, not only in the field of *falsafa*, but also in defining the historiographical ups and downs of the other tradition, i.e., *bayān*. Despite being considered fundamentally separate, no history of *bayān* can be written in detachment from *falsafa*. While scholarship, especially during recent decades, has thoroughly examined the deleterious consequences of prejudiced historiography in the field of *falsafa*, the collateral misconceptions in the field of *bayān* remain sorely ignored.¹¹⁷

115 Ignác Goldziher, *Abhandlungen zur arabischen Philologie* (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1921), 155-81.

116 Ritter, “Religiöse Orthodoxie,” 142-3.

117 For an insightful account of different approaches in the historiography of philosophy in the Islamic world, see Ulrich Rudolph, “Introduction,” in *Philosophy in the Islamic World Online: 8th–10th Centuries*, ed. Ulrich Rudolph, Rotraud Hansberger and Peter Adamson, trans. by Rotraud Hansberger

Ğurğānī in his intellectual engagement is perceived and represented within a certain conceptual framework stemming from and corresponding to the Greek philosophical tradition dominated by the polarity between philosophy and literature. As a result, scholars investigating his thought have no way but to place him within the context of a *bayān* that stands in opposition to *falsafa*, thus dismissing from the outset its *philosophical* merit and relevance. This perspective eliminated the possibility of considering *bayān* as if *falsafa* did not exist. This is why, *bayān* usually referred to as *balāġa*, came to be considered as the Arabic counterpart to the Aristotelian Rhetoric, in a loose sense that extends as well to poetics. As a consequence, the main approaches to his intellectual output, whether psychological, aesthetic, or literary, led to an exclusive or strong focus on the issue of Greek influences on Ğurğānī himself and on the tradition of *bayān* in general.

The problem was not so much that *language*, as the self-declared subject matter of Ğurğānī's intellectual engagement,¹¹⁸ was reduced to *poetry* or more broadly *literary language*. His works obviously allowed such a reading in terms of literary criticism or aesthetic theory, even if they are anachronistic. It was, however, problematic that language was understood within an Aristotelian conceptual framework as isolated from and contrasted to thought. Thus, the condition for the possibility of a conceptualization of language that denies such an isolation failed from the outset.¹¹⁹ The systematic divide between the language of proof and the language of poetry constitutes the general assumption that underlies not only the study and historiography of *falsafa* in the Islamic world up to this day, but also of *bayān* both within the geographical borders of Islamic lands and beyond them, particularly in Europe.

Upon closer examination, the dividing line between the so-called *insider* and *outsider* scholars who contributed to the reception and reconstruction of our image of Ğurğānī as a thinker dissolves. Insofar as they all eventually come to emphasize *taste* and represent Ğurğānī's project accordingly as a "gustatory philosophy," "literary theory," "poetics," or similar designations that are all anachronistically applied to Ğurğānī's intellectual activity, no justifiable distinction can be made between those who completely dismiss the *falsafa*-tainted *bayān* ('Abduh and his affiliates), those who completely deny any purely Arabic *bayān* by revealing its entangled evolving history to highlight its fundamental debt to *falsafa* and Greek heritage (Ĥusayn) and those trying to find a way in between either by rediscovering the Arabic element in a *bayān* modeled on a Greek precedent (Ĥalafallāh) or by representing it as an original and independent science evolving out of Arabs' taste and "remarkable talent for literary art" (Ritter). Each of these scholars engaged with Ğurğānī in a unique manner,

(Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2016), 1-28, esp. 1-11, and 21-28. König-Pralong incisively analyzes the beginnings of representing Arabs as the other for constructing the European identity in its historical and scientific contexts around 1800, see Catherine König-Pralong, "Alterität, fremde Nähe und Hybridisierung: Die Araber in der Philosophiegeschichte um 1800," in *Philosophiegeschichte in globaler Perspektive*, ed. Rolf Eberfeld (Hamburg: Felix Meiner, 2017), 231–51. For a rich collected volume on the historiography of Arabic philosophy from various perspectives, see *La Philosophie arabe à l'étude : sens, limites et défis d'une discipline moderne*, ed. Jean-Baptist Brenet and Olga Lizzini (Paris: Librairie Philosophique J. Vrin, 2019).

118 Ğurğānī, *Asrār*, ed. Hellmut Ritter, 2-3.

119 For an attempt at showing the fruitfulness of approaching *bayān* from this perspective, see Mostafa Najafi, *Fakhr al-Dīn al-Rāzī's Philosophical Theory of Language Between Mantīq and Bayān* (Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter, forthcoming).

with particular presuppositions, distinctive concerns, and specific hopes that do not coincide. Under the influence of various scientific and non-scientific factors, they had different points of departure. Yet, they all ended up situating Ġurġānī and his works within the paradigm of a polar opposition between philosophy and literature in the latter domain. While ‘Abduh and his affiliates pursue the political privilege of the Arabic language and through that the revival of the Arabic Islamic world, Ḥusayn and Ritter seek to open new paths for the renaissance of the Islamic world maintaining the contrast between poetry and philosophy. All such roads seem to lead in the wrong direction.

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